

TABLE I

(Figures represent the percentage of the substrate utilised.)

o hr.	Semicarbazide.				Butylamine.		
	10 ⁻² .	10 ⁻³ .	10 ⁻⁴ .	10 ⁻⁵ .	10 ⁻⁶ .	10 ⁻² .	10 ⁻³ .
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0
6	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.6	28.6	0.0	0.0
8	0.0	0.0	10.6	23.1	50.0	0.0	0.0
10	0.0	8.0	21.1	34.7	57.2	0.0	10.0
12	6.7	12.0	36.9	46.2	64.3	0.0	20.0
14	13.4	24.0	42.2	57.7	85.8	0.0	30.0
16	20.0	36.0	52.7	69.3	100.0	0.0	45.0
18	24.0	40.0	...	...	...	0.0	...
20	34.3	...	...	100.0	...	5.3	60.0
22	40.0	...	...	...	...	15.8	70.0
24	...	...	94.8	...	...	...	...
26	...	...	100.0	...	...	34.2	90.0
28	...	...	84.0	...	...	42.2	...
29	...	...	...	...	...	...	100.0
30	70.7	88.0	...	...	...	57.9	...
32	73.4	96.0	...	...	...	68.5	...
34	80.0	100.0	...	...	...	84.2	...
36	85.7	...	...	...	...	89.4	...
38	90.7	...	...	...	...	100.0	...
40	100.0	...	...	...	...	...	...

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ON CUPRIC ETHYL ACETOACETATE

By G. SITARAMAIAH

The number of neutral chelate oxygen complexes with divalent copper is very large; the ethyl acetoacetate derivative forms crystals of peculiar green colour, insoluble in water and soluble in common organic solvents (Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 3153). Calvin and Wilson studied the stability of this chelate by the p_x titration method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003). During the present investigation the composition of this chelate has been studied by the thermometric titration method of Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, **19**, 324).

The experimental arrangement for the thermometric titration was the same, as used by Halder (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 147) and the titrations were done taking all the precautions laid down. The copper salt solution (50 c.c.) was taken in the Dewar flask and titrated with an alcoholic solution of acetoacetic ester. The change in temperature after each addition of the ester was noted with a Beckmann thermometer.

Analar copper sulphate pentahydrate was used to prepare the solutions; the solutions had a strength of $M/8$ with respect to sodium acetate, which was used to raise the p_H of the solutions. The ester solutions were all made in 50% alcohol (v/v).

FIG. 1

I	0.05569 M Cu^{2+}	with	0.5432 M ester
II	0.03656 M	„	0.3103 M „
III	0.02352 M	„	0.2483 M „
IV	0.01919 M	„	0.1901 M „

In Fig. 1, the total change of temperature was plotted against the volume of ester added. All the curves show that the complex cupric ethyl acetoacetate formed during the titrations has the composition, $Cu(C_6H_9O_3)_2$. Thus, the thermometric study corroborates the conclusion drawn about the composition of this complex, by other methods.

The author's best thanks are due to Dr. R. D. Gupta, Head of the Dept. of Chemistry, for his keen interest in the subject and helpful suggestions.

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